

MERICS

Mercator Institute for China Studies

MERICS Europe-China Resilience Audit

The **MERICS Europe-China Resilience Audit** maps vulnerabilities and resilience across Europe in relation to China. It examines ten selected EU countries (Czechia, France, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Lithuania, Netherlands, Poland, Spain, Sweden) and the United Kingdom, building on a database featuring 98 indicators across for domains – economy, security, politics and society. The research is part of the project “**Dealing with a resurgent China**”, funded by the EU’s Horizon Europe research and innovation program.

picture alliance / Hans Lucas | Union
Européenne

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Resilience Index overview

European comparison: vulnerabilities are widespread - resilience-building efforts have been uneven

Levels of vulnerability and resilience towards China

Vulnerability Index: ■ Far above average ■ Above average ■ Average ■ Below average ■ Far below average
 Resilience Index: ■ Far above average ■ Above average ■ Average ■ Below average ■ Far below average

Note: Results are only comparable within each category (economy, security, politics, society).

Source: MERICS

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In recent years, China-related risks have become more apparent and acute for Europe. The discussion on how to manage those risks is at the heart of Europe's adjustment of its China policy. To contribute to this process, this audit provides a comparative assessment, confirming significant differences in vulnerabilities and progress on resilience building measures towards China between the 11 countries covered.

[Read the analysis here](#)

Country profiles - vulnerability and resilience

Czech Republic's China policy reorientation limits its vulnerabilities

France has a very uneven approach to resilience-building

Germany prioritizes economic and societal resilience

Hungary shows limited commitment to enhancing its China resilience

Italy's resilience-building measures do not match its vulnerabilities

Lithuania's resilience benefits from minimal exposure to China

The Netherlands has a robust approach to resilience

Poland has a long way to go in resilience

Spain's resilience-building work has been limited

building

building

to certain issues

Sweden leads in resilience building, except in the economic sphere

The United Kingdom excels in resilience building, except in the economic sphere

Publications

The Europe-
China Resilience
Audit: Insights
for advancing
European
resilience

Oct 31, 2024

Profiling
European coun-
tries' resilience
towards China

Oct 31, 2024

Building re-
silience: The
need for a geopo-
litical European
Commission and

strong leadership from Member States

Oct 31, 2024

European re- silience will re- quire a more proactive ap- proach to partnerships

Oct 31, 2024

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